

FPGA IMPLEMENTATION OF A SIMPLE LOSSLESS ALGORITHM (SLA) FOR ON-BOARD SATELLITE HYPERSPECTRAL DATA COMPRESSION

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1. INTRODUCTION

Increasing resolution of imaging sensors unfold a range of applications, which can use this on-board satellite data in real time or near real time scenarios for earth observation, weather forecast, etc. To deal with this large amount of data acquired, on-board data processing becomes essential and whole chain of activities from data capturing to application end needs to be upgraded accordingly. On-board image compression is a critical aspect while designing on-board processing systems, which needs to be updated to match the evolving requirements. Hyperspectral imaging offers detailed information using multiple bands, allowing complete analysis of the target scene. As ground sample distance of hyperspectral imagers is reducing, data rate of sensors is receiving quadratic growth [1]. This calls for hyperspectral data compression to match channel bandwidth requirements so as to avoid data loss, especially in case of on-board satellite scenarios, where there is a constraint on the available resources. This calls for improved performance in algorithmic as well as hardware architecture level.

For hardware implementation of on-board satellite compression methods, FPGAs and application specific integrated circuits (ASIC) are the key platforms, keeping in mind the available power requirements [2]. However, GPUs and other commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) platforms are also being used for computationally intense part of algorithm [3]. FPGAs provide an added advantage of re-configurability and optimizations specific to the architecture, which makes them most sought after platform for on-board applications. From hardware perspectives, out of the two broad class of methods used for on-board compression i.e. transform and prediction based methods, transform based methods are more resource as well as time consuming. On the other hand, prediction based methods such as differential pulse code modulation (DPCM), look up table (LUT), clustered DPCM, region of interest (ROI), distributed source coding (DSC), adaptive filter based methods, etc. [4-7] are computationally simpler, but throughput and resource requirement needs to be optimized. Some best performing lossless methods for hyperspectral image compression include fast lossless (FL) algorithm, which later modified and used in consultative committee for space data system (CCSDS) 123.0-B-1 standards. CCSDS 123.0-B-1 utilizes inherent spectral and spatial correlation of hyperspectral images and achieves best compression performance among other methods used previously. However, implementation complexity of weight update causes a trade-off between parallel processing and memory requirements [8,9]. Similarly, data processing order also has considerable trade-off between throughput and memory requirements and depending on the mission requirement, either throughput or resource performance is improved [10]. There are many hardware architectures proposed in literature for CCSDS 123.0-B-1, where bottleneck of weight update loop, throughput or computational complexity is targeted at a time [11]. These architectures use various tools to achieve high performance e.g. storage-calculate trade-off, efficient calculations, pipelining, parallel processing, etc. Real time requirement set by the CCSDS standard is 20 Msamples/sec, which is crossed in literature using above techniques [12].

To leverage the inherent correlation in hyperspectral images i.e. spectral and spatial correlation simultaneously with low computation complexity, a prediction based simple lossless algorithm (SLA) for on-board satellite hyperspectral data compression is proposed [13]. SLA is designed to transfer calculation load towards previously processed pixels with lesser data dependencies, so that parallel processing can be utilized to achieve higher throughput. [13] shows reduced calculations involving current pixel, which decreases timing requirements to process a pixel. In addition to that, pipelining is also an option to reduce the latency involved.

This paper presents an FPGA architecture of SLA on Xilinx Virtex Ultrascale+ VCU118 evaluation kit. Band sequential (BSQ) order is used for data processing. Resource requirement among modes of SLA is compared with CCSDS 123.0-B-1 standards along with timing details. The comparisons validate trade-off between compression performance and resource utilization among different modes of SLA and presents SLA as an alternate for on-board satellite hyperspectral data compression with low complexity and high speed. Shift registers are used to design a serial-in-parallel-out (SIPO)

register for storing neighbourhood pixels required for processing and previous band pixels are stored in block RAM IP.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows: section 2 provides an overview of SLA. Memory requirements, timing diagrams and other FPGA architecture related aspects are covered in section 3. Section 4 shows comparison of SLA with existing methods and CCSDS 123.0-B-1 for resource utilization and timing requirements. Section 5 concludes the paper with future directions.

2. OVERVIEW OF SLA

SLA is a prediction based lossless hyperspectral image compression algorithm, which is designed for on-board satellite applications, considering the resource limitations and error prone environment. SLA uses concepts of nearest neighbour and non-binary tree traversal in pre-processing stage to allow minimum computational complexity and decisions are made using a selection strategy called as neighbour driven decision making (NDDM) to avoid search and storage for optimum operand. Depending on the correlation in the image, combination of previously processed pixels selects appropriate operand for the current pixel [13].

SLA uses two type of arithmetic units in pre-processing stage, which are calculation and selection units. Selection unit compares pre-processed values of previously processed pixels to choose best neighbour for processing current pixel. Calculation unit involves minimal use of current pixel along with previously processed pixels. Thus, SLA reduces calculation load of current pixel and it has to undergoes ~20% of total calculations [13]. SLA is a positive integer based method, which is implemented using a simple mapping function to convert negative numbers to positive. Output of pre-processing stage i.e. minimized prediction residual is then encoded using sample adaptive Golomb encoding [13].

SLA has four directional modes viz. west, north, spectral and four causal neighbour, which are decided based on the correlation of hyperspectral image. Depending on the directional mode and neighbour driven decision making (NDDM), selector unit chooses the appropriate neighbour for decision making. As these neighbours are already processed, it allows selector units to take decisions before arrival of current pixel [13].

3. FPGA ARCHITECTURE OF SLA

This section deals with FPGA architecture of SLA along with timing information and memory distribution and estimation. Depending on the mode of SLA, different architectural aspect becomes prominent.

3.1 Schematic for FPGA architecture of SLA

The schematic of FPGA architecture of SLA is presented for directional four causal neighbour mode in fig.1. This mode is chosen as it has maximum memory requirements among all modes of SLA and only this mode uses two previously processed bands i.e. (z-1) and (z-2) for pre-processing stage. The incoming sensor data is simultaneously written into block RAM (BRAM) of FPGA as well as customized shift register based serial-in-parallel-out (SIPO) to allow required availability of data.

3.2 Timing diagram for full directional west mode of SLA

Timing diagram of directional west mode of SLA is presented, because this mode is having maximum constraints among all modes regarding the operation of selector unit. Full directional west of SLA assumes predominant west correlation between pixels, thus it makes decisions for current pixel processing using west neighbour of current pixel. As incoming data rate will decide the maximum available time interval to make decisions, this mode is having stringent timing requirements in comparison to other modes of SLA. As shown in fig.2, data arrives at starting time and simultaneously wide neighbourhood local sum (wnls) and local difference (ld) decision blocks start operations for next pixel. Similarly, other blocks start operations in consequent timing cycle and pipelining is used for efficient implementation.

Fig.1. Schematic for hardware architecture of four causal neighbor mode of SLA

Fig.2. Timing diagram of pre-processing stage for full west directional mode of SLA

3.3 Memory distribution for spatial and spectral requirements

For processing of a pixel, SLA uses spatial as well as spectral neighbours of current pixel. For directional west mode of SLA, spatial neighbourhood requirements are shown in fig.3(a), where decision is made using immediate west neighbour and pixel requirement is increased. Thus, depending on the mode of SLA, requirement of neighbourhood pixels' changes. Customized shift register based memory is designed to allow access of neighbouring pixels in the current band and BRAMs are used to store previous band data. Based on these information, memory estimation is done for all modes of SLA. Fig.3(b) shows shift register based SIPO design, which involves shifting of current pixel in a manner that all pixels are made available as per the requirement. Horizontal dimension of incoming image decides the size of this memory.

Fig.3(a). Spatial neighborhood of current pixel for west mode

Fig.3(b). Shift register based memory for spatial neighborhood for west mode

Spectral neighbourhood requirements are met using combination of block RAM IP of FPGA and customized SIPO design. Incoming current pixel is simultaneously given as input to both memory blocks. SIPO block discards the data once it has completed shift cycle of particular mode, whereas BRAM IP of size of spectral band allows storage and access of pixels from complete previous band.

3.3 Memory estimation for all modes of SLA

Based on discussion of previous sub-sections, estimation of memory requirements of pre-processing stage for all modes of SLA is done in BSQ scanning order and shown in table I. It can be seen that previous spectral band requires a BRAM IP of spectral band size i.e. $N_x \times N_y$, which increases memory requirements in comparison to other modes.

TABLE I
ESTIMATED MEMORY SIZE OF PRE-PROCESSING FOR ALL MODES OF SLA IN BSQ ORDER

Mode of SLA		West	North	Spectral	Four causal neighbour
Total memory requirements	SIPO size	N_x+4	$(2 \times N_x)+3$	N_x+3	$2 \cdot (N_x+3)$
	BRAM IP of size $N_x \times N_y$	1	1	2	2

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section deals with results and estimates obtained using FPGA implementation of SLA, which is done on Xilinx Virtex Ultrascale+ VCU118 evaluation kit. The implementation is done using band sequential order (BSQ) for current work. RTL codes are written in Verilog using single controlling clock for all modules of 1 GHz. Comparison of proposed FPGA architecture of SLA is done with hardware implementations of CCSDS 123.0-B-1 standard. Memory requirements, overall resource utilization hierarchy is presented and compared. Timing and estimated throughput are also discussed.

4.1 Comparison of estimated memory requirements

Table II compares estimated memory requirements of SLA with different proposed hardware architectures for CCSDS 123.0-B-1 standards. Pre-processing stage is compared in both the methods to keep comparisons uniform as the pre-processing block of CCSDS 123.0-B-1 standards is been implemented with various encoding methods. Maximum memory requirement among all modes of SLA is used for comparison. Architectures proposed in [6] are chosen based on calculation and store trade-off strategy for different parameters [6]. It is observed that some architectures require less memory resources, but in turn the number of calculation for processing a pixel increases [6].

4.2 Resource utilization

In present implementation, SLA uses Xilinx simple dual port BRAM IP of 16-bit port width and 1024×1024 port depth. These specifications are chosen to cover maximum 16-bit input dynamic range and spectral band of maximum size

1024*1024. To read data from IP port, there is an inherent latency of 2 clock cycles from read clock. Thus, to match the neighbourhood pixel requirements, read clock of IP is initiated three clock cycles before arrival of current pixel and stored

TABLE II
COMPARISON OF ESTIMATED MEMORY SIZE FOR PRE-PROCESSING STAGE IN BSQ
SCANNING ORDER FOR SPECTRAL BAND OF SIZE (Nx*Ny)

Hardware architectures in BSQ order	Estimated memory requirements
CCSDS 123.0-B-1 [11]	$(Nx+1).D+Nx.Ny.P.(D+4)+3.(D+4)+Cz.WCR$
CCSDS 123.0-B-1 [11]	$(P+1).Nx.D+Cz.(D+4)+Nz.Cz.WCR$
CCSDS 123.0-B-1 [11]	$5.(P+1).D+Cz.(D+4)+Cz.WCR$
CCSDS 123.0-B-1 [11]	$3.(P+1).D+2.D+Cz.(D+4)+Cz.WCR$
CCSDS 123.0-B-1 [12]	$(Nx+1).D+P.Nx.Ny.(D+3)+Cz.(\Omega+3)+D$
Present work	$2.(Nx+3)+2.Nx.Ny$

in SIPO.

Hierarchical resource utilization of four causal neighbour mode of SLA is presented in table III, which shows that factor selection block is using maximum resources in comparison to other calculation or selection blocks. These resources, however, are used by previously processed pixels and are performed before arrival of the current pixel. Second most resource utilization is of BRAM IP core, which is designed to accommodate maximum possible data and covers a high dynamic range. Current pixel processing undergoes minimal computations, resultantly using less resources. Further, spectral band memory is using maximum resources as its designed to accommodate larger data size with 16-bit resolution.

TABLE III
RESOURCE UTILIZATION HIERARCHY FOR FOUR CAUSAL NEIGHBOR MODE OF SLA

Name of DUT	CLB LUTs	CLB Registers	CARRY8	F7 Muxes	F8 Muxes	F9 Muxes	Block RAM Tile	URAM	DSPs	Bonded IOB	Global clock buffer
dff_0	139	16	18	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
dff	183	16	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
blk_mem	2592	132	0	640	320	0	960	0	0	0	0
sipo	2206	298	164	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ls	440	30	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ld	311	64	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
factor_min	27	32	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
smt_min	0	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
ld_selector	1002	51	67	16	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
fac_selector	1704	161	98	38	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
smt_selector	60	32	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TOP MODULE	8788	969	421	724	320	0	960	0	0	58	2

4.3 Timing performance and estimated throughput

From previous sections, it's derived that there is no dependency between pixels for pre-processing, parallel processing can be used effectively to attain high level of throughput. As shown in timing diagram above, pipelining is used to reduce the latency, which is observed to be 4 clock cycles after data arrival.

Further, simulations are performed successfully at clock frequency of 1GHz with initial latency of 4ns. This allows to estimate the throughput in higher Msamples/sec range. As, dynamic range is set to be 16-bits, present implementation of

SLA is expected to have a throughput in Gb/sec range. However, to meet this high clock requirements, parallel processing will be used with multiple cores of SLA to establish the observation.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In this paper, we discussed hardware architecture for FPGA implementation of SLA using customized shift register based memory and BRAM IP of Xilinx FPGA. Memory requirements are discussed for SLA and are compared with different hardware architectures proposed for CCSDS 123.0-B-1 standard. Timing and resource utilization for present architecture is presented. The observations made from architecture and simulations estimate high throughput of SLA, which will be verified by using multiple cores of SLA along with real-time data inputs.

Further, efficient memory design will be done to store previously processed pixels and possibility of in-memory-computing will be explored. BIP and BIL scanning order will be tested for efficient implementations and finally, custom IC implementation will be attempted.

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